

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Two

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ Why are the nations in an uproar and the peoples devising a vain thing?</p>	<p>לָמָּה רָגְשׁוּ גוֹיִם וּלְאֻמִּים יִהְיוּ-</p>
<p>² The kings of the earth take their stand and the rulers take counsel together against the LORD and against His Anointed, saying,</p>	<p>רִיק : ² יִתְיַצְּבוּ אֶרֶץ וְרוֹזְנִים נוֹסְדוּ יַחַד עַל-יְהוָה וְעַל-מְשִׁיחוֹ : ³ גִּנְתָּקָה אֶת-מִוֹסְרוֹתֵימוֹ וְנִשְׁלִיכָה מִמֶּנּוּ עֲבֹתֵימוֹ : ⁴ יוֹשֵׁב בַּשָּׁמַיִם יִשְׁחַק אֶרְצֵנוּ יִלְעַג-לָמוֹ : ⁵</p>
<p>³ "Let us tear their fetters apart and cast away their cords from us!"</p>	<p>אֲזִי יִדְבַר אֱלֹהֵינוּ בְּאָפוֹ וּבַחֲרוֹנוֹ יִבְהַלְמוּ : ⁶ וְאֲנִי נִסְכַּתִּי מִלְּפִי עַל-צִיּוֹן הַר-קְדְּשֵׁי : ⁷ אֲסַפְּרָה אֵל חַק יְהוָה אֲמַר אֵלַי בְּנֵי אֶתְּהָ אֲנִי הַיּוֹם יִלְדֶּתִיךָ : ⁸ שְׁאַל מִמֶּנִּי וְאֶתַּנַּח גוֹיִם נִחַלְתֶּךָ וְאֶחֱזַתְךָ אֶפְסֵי-אֶרֶץ : ⁹</p>
<p>⁴ He who sits in the heavens laughs, the Lord scoffs at them.</p>	<p>תִּרְעַם בְּשִׁבְט בְּרוֹזַל כִּכְלִי יוֹצֵר תִּנְפְּצֵם : ¹⁰ וְעַתָּה מְלָכִים הִשְׁכִּילוּ הַיּוֹסְדוּ שִׁפְטֵי אֶרֶץ : ¹¹ עֲבְדוּ אֶת-יְהוָה בִּירְאָה וְגִילוּ בְרַעְדָּה : ¹²</p>
<p>⁵ Then He will speak to them in His anger and terrify them in His fury, saying,</p>	<p>נִשְׁקוּ-בָר פֶּן-יֵאָנַף וְתֵאָבְדוּ דָרְךְ כִּי-יִבְעַר כַּמְעַט אָפוֹ אֲשֶׁר־כָּל-חֹסֵי בוֹ :</p>
<p>⁶ "But as for Me, I have installed My King Upon Zion, My holy mountain."</p>	<p></p>
<p>⁷ "I will surely tell of the decree of the LORD: He said to Me, 'You are My Son, today I have begotten You.</p>	<p></p>
<p>⁸ 'Ask of Me, and I will surely give the nations as Your inheritance, and the <i>very</i> ends of the earth as Your possession.</p>	<p></p>
<p>⁹ 'You shall break them with a rod of iron, you shall shatter them like earthenware.'"</p>	<p></p>
<p>¹⁰ Now therefore, O kings, show discernment; take warning, O judges of the earth.</p>	<p></p>
<p>¹¹ Worship the LORD with reverence and rejoice with trembling.</p>	<p></p>
<p>¹² Do homage to the Son, that He not become angry, and you perish <i>in</i> the way, for His wrath may soon be kindled. How blessed are all who take refuge in Him!</p>	<p></p>

Targum

¹ Why are the Gentiles disturbed, and the nations murmuring vanity? ² The kings of the earth arise and the rulers will join together to rebel in the LORD's presence, and to strive against his Anointed. ³ They say, "Let us break their bonds, and let us throw off their chains from us." ⁴ The one who sits in heaven will laugh; the word of the LORD will mock at them. ⁵ Then he will speak to them in his strength, and in his wrath he will frighten them. ⁶ I have anointed my king, and appointed him over my sanctuary. ⁷ I will tell of the covenant of the LORD. He said: "You are as dear to me as a son to a father (abba), pure as if this day I had created you." ⁸ Ask me and I will give the riches of the Gentiles as your inheritance, the rulers of the ends of the earth as your holding. ⁹ You will shatter them as with a rod of iron, like a potter's vessel you will break them. ¹⁰ And now, O kings, grow wise; accept discipline, O princes of the earth. ¹¹ Worship in the presence of the LORD with fear, and pray with trembling. ¹² Accept instruction lest he be angry, and you lose your way; for his wrath will tarry a little. Happy all who trust in his word!

Interlinear

Psa. 2:1	Why	are	the	nations	in	an	uproar	
Lex	מָה			גוֹי			רִגֵּשׁ	
Lex Trl	mah			goy			ragash	
And	the	peoples	devising	a	vain	thing		
		לְאֹמ	הִגָּה		רִיק	רִיק		
		le'om	hagah		riq	riq		
Psa. 2:2	The	kings	of	the	earth	take	their	stand
Lex		מְלָכִי			אֶרֶץ	יָצַב		יָצַב
Lex Trl		melekh			'eretz	yatzav		yatzav
And	the	rulers	take	counsel	together			
		רָזַן	יָסַד	יָסַד	יַחַד			
		razan	yasad	yasad	yachad			
Against	the	Lord	and	against	His	Anointed	saying	
עַל		יְהוָה		עַל		מָשִׁיחַ		
'al		yhwh		'al		mashiach		
Psa. 2:3	Let	us	tear	their	fetters	apart	And	
Lex			נָתַק		מוֹסָר	נָתַק		
Lex Trl			nataq		musar	nataq		
cast	away	their	cords	from	us			
שָׁלַךְ	שָׁלַךְ		עֲבֹת					
shalakh	shalakh		'avot					
Psa. 2:4	He	who	sits	in	the	heavens		
Lex			יָשַׁב			שָׁמַיִם		
Lex Trl			yashav			shamayim		
laughs	The	Lord						
שָׂחַק		אֲדֹנָי						
sachaq		'adonay						
scoffs	at	them						

לַעֲג
la'ag

Psa. 2:5 Then He will speak to them in His anger
Lex אָז אַף
Lex Trl 'az 'af

And terrify them in His fury saying
בְּהֵל חֲרוֹן
bahal charon

Psa. 2:6 But as for Me I have installed My King
Lex נָסַךְ מֶלֶךְ
Lex Trl nasakh melekh

Upon Zion My holy mountain
צִיּוֹן קֹדֶשׁ הַר
tzion qodesh har

Psa. 2:7 I will surely tell of the decree of the
Lex כִּי סָפַר חֹק
Lex Trl ki safar choq

Lord He said to Me You are My Son
יהוה אמר אָמַר בֶּן
yhwh 'amar 'amar ben

Today I have begotten You
יום יָלַד
yom yalad

Psa. 2:8 Ask of Me and I will surely give the
Lex שָׂאֵל נָתַן
Lex Trl sha'al natan

nations as Your inheritance And the very
גוֹי נַחֲלָה
goy nachalah

ends of the earth as Your possession
אֲפֵס אֶרֶץ אַחֲזָזָה
'efes 'eretzh 'achuzzah

Psa. 2:9 You shall break them with a rod of iron
 Lex רָעַע שֵׁבֶט בַּרְזֶל
 Lex Trl ra'ac shevet barzel

You shall shatter them like earthenware
 נָפַץ
 nafatz

earthenware earthenware
 כֵּלִי יָצַר
 keli yatzar

Psa. 2:10 Now therefore O kings
 Lex עֲתָה מְלִיכִים
 Lex Trl 'attah melekh

show discernment Take warning
 שָׁחַל שָׁחַל יָסַר יָסַר
 sakhal sakhal yasar yasar

O judges of the earth
 שֹׁפֵט אֶרֶץ
 shafat 'eretz

Psa. 2:11 Worship the Lord with reverence
 Lex עָבַד יְהוָה יִרְאָה
 Lex Trl 'avad yhw'ah yir'ah

And rejoice with trembling
 גִּיל רַעְדָּה
 gil re'adah

Psa. 2:12 Do homage to the Son that
 Lex נָשַׁק בֵּן
 Lex Trl nashaq nashaq bar

He not become angry and you perish in the way
 אָנַף אָנַף אָבַד דֶּרֶךְ
 'anaf 'anaf 'avad derekh

For His wrath may soon be kindled

אֵף
ʾaf

מֵאֵת
meʾat

בְּעַר
baʿar

How blessed are all who take refuge in Him
אֵשֶׁר
ʾeshher
כָּל
kol
חָסָה
chasah
חָסָה
chasah

Verse One and Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ Why are the nations in an uproar and the peoples devising a vain thing?</p> <p>² The kings of the earth take their stand and the rulers take counsel together against the LORD and against His Anointed, saying,</p>	<p>¹ לָמָּה רָגְשׁוּ גוֹיִם וְלְאֻמִּים יִהְגּוּ- רִיק׃ יִתְיַצְּבוּ מְלָכֵי-אֶרֶץ וְרוֹזְנִים נֹסְדוּ-יַחַד עַל-יְהוָה וְעַל-מְשִׁיחוֹ׃</p>

Verse Analysis

The life of a nation is tied to the life of the individuals who live in said nations. The people must want spiritual awareness in order to survive. The people and leaders need legal obedience to moral laws. Only through ethical and moral endeavors can the nations of the world be assured of the LORD's help.

Corruption by materialistic leaders will destroy a nation. It is best to have leaders who have one foot in the material world and the other foot in the spiritual world.

לָמָּה (lama) – means "why." Why is it important to be morally righteous? Only the morally righteous can be sure of aid and a future by following the LORD's sovereign rule.

רָגַשׁ (rag' sh) – means "to put in motion by some outside influence." This Psalm refers to the time when King David had solidified the kingdom. After King Saul's death his remaining sons attempted to take the throne of Israel. A civil war broke out for seven years. King David won the civil war and was putting the kingdom back together. The Philistines did not want David to have a strong Israel and prepared to attack them.

מְשִׁיחוֹ (m' sheecho) – means "anointed one." King David was anointed by the prophet Samuel for the LORD's house and the moral future of all mankind. The line of David produced Solomon, who built the LORD's house and Jesus the Messiah.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Why does the material driven Philistines gather to attack Israel? (v. 1)

Their king called an army together in secret to attack the LORD's people (Israel) and the LORD's King (David). (v. 2)

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
3 "Let us tear their fetters apart and cast away their cords from us!"	נִנְתְּקָה אֶת־מִוֹסְרוֹתֵינוּ וְנִשְׁלִיכָה מִמֶּנּוּ עֲבֹתֵינוּ :

Verse Analysis

נִנְתְּקָה (n'nat'cha) - means "to forcibly separate, to tear asunder." King David had created agreements between the tribes to work together as a nation. The survival of Israel depended upon the twelve tribes coming together to become one nation. If the tribes did not come together to form a nation, the individual tribes would have been picked off one by one. A central army needed to be created to fight any of the surrounding nations from attacking Israel. The book of Judges describes the time when the individual tribes were separate. During that time period, the surrounding nations attacked the different tribes. King David's army was able to establish a strong kingdom, and he expanded the territory of Israel.

עֲבֹתָ (avot) – means "a cord of which the forces of activity are harnessed." It infers the cords of a yoke (agreements to protect one another) between the various tribes, which created the nation of Israel. The cords that David created were spiritual. He told the people that they needed to remain loyal to the LORD, who brought them out of Egypt. The spiritual connection needed to be established between the tribes to create the nation.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The Philistines wanted to cut the spiritual cords between the people of Israel and the LORD.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
4 He who sits in the heavens laughs, the Lord scoffs at them.	יֹשֵׁב בַּשָּׁמַיִם יִשְׁחַק אֲדֹנָי יִלְעָג- לְמוֹדֵי

Verse Analysis

יֹשֵׁב (yasha) – means "to sit, remain, dwell." The LORD permits men to engage in lengthy experiments in the carrying out of their plans. He allows materialistically minded people to gather their earthly treasures hoping people will see the need for the spiritual world.

אֲדֹנָי (adonai) – means "my master." A person who refers to the LORD as Adonai is dedicated to serving the LORD. This person works for His purpose, wanting to learn about the spiritual world.

The LORD mocks people who are only interested in the material world.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD in Heaven laughs at people who are only interested in the material world, like the Philistines.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
⁵ Then He will speak to them in His anger and terrify them in His fury, saying,	אֵץ יְדַבֵּר אֱלִימוּ בְּאַפּוֹ וּבְתַרוּנוֹ יִבְהַלְמוּ׃

Verse Analysis

אֵץ יְדַבֵּר (atz y' dabar) – means "to seek enduring salvation without paying homage to the moral law."

The LORD is a free, moral, and personal God who rules over the material and physical world. The LORD hears the vain words of the earthly-minded Kings who are only interested in material conquests and is saddened that they have no interested in the spiritual world

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD hears the words of the Philistine king and responds to him in a way that terrifies the king's nation.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
6 "But as for Me, I have installed My King Upon Zion, My holy mountain."	וַאֲנִי נִסְכַּחְתִּי מֶלֶכִּי עַל-צִיּוֹן הַר- קֹדֶשׁ יְיָ

Verse Analysis

Jerusalem was a place on Earth that allows positive energy from the Right Column of the Tree of Life to enter Malkhut. The Zohar says that there are several places on the Earth where the positive energy of the right column can enter Malkhut. Also, several places on Earth allow the negative energy of the left column to enter. Unfortunately, the accumulation of negative energy in a specific place causes the Klippot of Evil Inclination to form.

The LORD had David anointed by Samuel to lead the LORD's people into the spiritual world. The LORD would not allow the Philistines to remove David as the King because he was chosen by the LORD and not by the people.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD anointed David because he could lead the people in their spiritual journey from the positive energy of Zion.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
7 "I will surely tell of the decree of the LORD: He said to Me, 'You are My Son, today I have begotten You.	אֲסַפְּרָה אֶל תִּקְיָה יְהוָה אֲמַר אֱלֹהִים בְּנֵי אֲתָתָה אֲנִי הַיּוֹם יְלִדְתִּיךָ :

Verse Analysis

אֲסַפְּרָה אֶל תִּקְיָה (asaf'ra el chok) means "recounting of facts with a movement toward a goal."

David was to be the spiritual light by being the righteous person of his generation. The Zohar says that there is at least one righteous person in every generation. King David was the righteous person of his generation. It was through the righteous that the LORD could send His Light to the people of the world.

"You are my son" means that David became the King because of the LORD's actions, not by the election of men. The LORD chose David because he desired to serve the LORD.

David's selection as a spiritual leader was something new that the LORD had done.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

David was obligated to proclaim: the LORD told him that he was selected by the LORD, not by humans, to lead the LORD's people to the spiritual world.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁸ Ask me and I will give the riches of the Gentiles as your inheritance, the rulers of the ends of the earth as your holding.</p>	<p>שְׁאַל מִפְּנֵי וְאֶתְּנָה גּוֹיִם נַחֲלָתְךָ וְאֶתְּנָתְךָ אֶפְסֵי-אֲרֶץ :</p>

Verse Analysis

The LORD told David to gird himself with purity, and so the people of the Earth would move forward toward the spiritual world. The inheritance is to cure the nations of the world of materialism. The will of the LORD can be done once the materialism of the Nefesh is removed.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD offered David the entire world so he could teach the people the ways of the LORD.

Verse Nine

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
9 'You shall break them with a rod of iron, you shall shatter them like earthenware.'"	תִּרְעֵם בְּשֵׁבֶט בַּרְזֶל כְּכֶלִי יוֹצֵר תִּנְפְצֵם :

Verse Analysis

The LORD instructed David that he should pray that the nations that surround his kingdom will submit to the spiritual light and ethical demands that he will bring them. When David conquered a nation, he brought the Light of Ein Sof with him. He was to teach them about the LORD. David's teaching would spread the Torah, thus the LORD's Will throughout the world. Any nation that decided to stay in the material world would be destroyed. Materialistic nations tend to fight other nations or themselves to gain more material wealth. Many times the fighting destroys the nation.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Any nation rising against David will be destroyed.

Verse

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
10 Now therefore, O kings, show discernment; take warning, O judges of the earth.	וְעַתָּה מְלָכִים הַשְׁכִּילוּ הַיּוֹסְרוֹ שֹׁפְטֵי אֶרֶץ׃

Verse Analysis

וְעַתָּה (v'ata) – means "and now." The LORD proclaimed the His design for Malkhut. Therefore, it must be implemented, comprehended and understood by the people in Malkhut.

הַשְׁכִּילוּ (has'keylou) – means "comprehend this."

שֹׁפְטֵי אֶרֶץ (shof'tai aretz) – means "to act as a law giver."

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Kings and judges of the Earth must learn about the spiritual world.

Verse Eleven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹¹ Worship the LORD with reverence and rejoice with trembling.</p>	<p>עֲבַדְוּ אֶת־יְהוָה בְּיִרְאָה וְגִיל׃ בְּרַעְדָּה׃</p>

Verse Analysis

עֲבַדְוּ (ev' do) – means "consecrate yourself to the service of the LORD." The spiritual world needs to be brought to the people in Malkhut. It is difficult for people who are prosperous materialistically to understand that there is more to the world than material wealth. Materialism is necessary because the Sefirah Malkhut is a physically-based Sefirah. However, the spiritual world of Yesod and the Upper World is critical for the Ruach to comprehend before the death of the Nefesh. David's role was to bring that understanding. Paying reverence to the LORD is the understanding that there is a spiritual world and the need to be a part of it. Trembling is a physical response of the Light of Ein Sof, which is overwhelming to those who are new to the experience.

וְגִיל׃ בְּרַעְדָּה׃ (v'geelou beer' ada) means "greatest joy, most joyous emotion." It is with great joy that one accepts the spiritual world that the LORD has created for our Ruach to return to. The Lower Waters of the Tree of Life is where our image of the LORD resides. The Ruach must be taught about the spiritual world. It is joyous to be able to live in Malkhut and keep all of the LORD's laws.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Remember that while rejoicing, one must revere the LORD so that no Law is broken.

Verse Twelve

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹² Do homage to the Son, that He not become angry, and you perish <i>in</i> the way, for His wrath may soon be kindled. How blessed are all who take refuge in Him!</p>	<p>נִשְׁקוּ-בָרַךְ בְּיָמֵי-אֵנֶף וְלֹתְאֲבָדוֹ דָּרָךְ כִּי-יִבְעַר כְּמַעַט אַפּוֹ אֲשֶׁר־י כָּל- חַוְסֵי בּוֹ</p>

Verse Analysis

The path of lawless persons leads to destruction and will eventually disappear. A goal of life is to return to Yesod. Therefore, stride forward toward salvation by trusting the LORD and always asking for His help. King David never forgot that the LORD placed him on the throne of Israel. He always asked for the LORD's help through his prayers. People today should be doing the same thing.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Yearn for the way of the spiritual world because any other path leads to doom and the anger of the LORD. Praise the LORD always and place your trust in Him, and He will show you the path to the spiritual world.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

¹ Why does the material driven Philistines gather to attack Israel?

² Their king called an army together in secret to attack the LORD's people (Israel) and the LORD's King (David).

³ The Philistines wanted to cut the spiritual cords between the people of Israel and the LORD.

⁴ The LORD in Heaven laughs at people who are only interested in the material world, like the Philistines.

⁵ The LORD hears the words of the Philistine king and responds to him in a way that terrifies the king's nation.

⁶ The LORD anointed David because he could lead the people in their spiritual journey from the positive energy of Zion.

⁷ David was obligated to proclaim: the LORD told him that he was selected by the LORD, not by humans, to lead the LORD's people to the spiritual world.

⁸ The LORD offered David the entire world so he could teach the people the ways of the LORD.

⁹ Any nation rising against David will be destroyed.

¹⁰ Kings and judges of the Earth must learn about the spiritual world.

¹¹ Remember that while rejoicing, one must revere the LORD so that no Law is broken.

¹² Yearn for the way of the spiritual world because any other path leads to doom and the anger of the LORD. Praise the LORD always and place your trust in Him, and He will show you the path to the spiritual world.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

